

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSES OF ENHANCED CORROSION BARRIER FOR POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A 3D FE model has been developed to predict diffusion and permeation through a nanocomposite matrix with uniform flake arrangement perpendicular to the direction of concentration gradient. The model showed good correlation with published analytical solutions. Based on this verification, the numerical model was extended to cover cases with no known accurate analytical solutions, *i.e.* flake angles. The combined influence of flake angles and slit width has been investigated, to understand the impact of changes to these variables. In addition, stress in the nanocomposite was also considered in the analyses, comparing the effects of different stress levels on diffusion. Comparisons were made between the current 3D models and previously developed 2D models to demonstrate the effectiveness of the latter for quick screening of non-critical variables.

1 INTRODUCTION

Corrosion is a long-standing issue in offshore oil and gas (O&G) structures, either externally from the harsh seawater environment, or internally from corrosive fluids being transported through pipelines. Surface protection of these structures are primarily polymer coatings, liners or paints, which degrade through continuous exposure. In order to increase their reliability, the permeability of moisture into the protective coatings should be reduced or even eliminated. Hence, enhancing the barrier properties of polymers can produce high performance, cost effective coatings and liners for pipelines and other similarly corrosion-prone structures.

Nanocomposites consisting of nanoscale reinforcements, *e.g.* carbon nanotubes and graphene, dispersed in a matrix material, *e.g.* a polymer, have been shown to enhance certain properties such as permeation barrier, tensile strength and wear performance [1-3]. As a permeation barrier, the nanofillers introduce a tortuous path for the fluids diffusing and permeating through the matrix material, as shown in Figure 1.

In a previous study by the authors [4], two-dimensional (2D) finite element (FE) models were successfully used to solve Fick's law of diffusion, predicting the barrier improvement in a nanocomposite as a function of flake dimension and orientation. The model assumed a unit cell matrix with uniformly distributed rectangular-shaped "barrier" flakes of dimensions $a/2$ by $2d$ that will introduce a more tortuous path to the permeants, as illustrated in Figure 1. It correlated well with the Minelli [5] analytical model for uniformly distributed flakes. Based on this verification, the 2D model was extended to consider the effects of angled flakes that more resembled the actual situation in real-life nanocomposites. The main observation from this study was the effect of angled flakes in constricting the pathway of permeants. For a fixed unit cell size, when flakes have zero angle, $\theta=0$, as shown in Figure 2, the flakes would be at maximum distance, b , from one another. Figure 3 shows the flakes at angle, θ , with smaller 'channels' for permeants to flow through. This effectively would increase the barrier property of the nanocomposite. It was also concluded from the work that the effect

of slit width, $2c$, *i.e.* in-plane separation between adjacent flakes, would diminish at higher flake angles. When flakes are slightly angled, smaller slit widths would increase the barrier property, whereas at higher angles, the effect was found to be insignificant because the adjacent flakes would come closer together, effectively forming a single and longer path for the permeants, as illustrated in Figure 3b.

In the present work, as an extension of the 2D models, three-dimensional (3D) FE models were developed in a bid to obtain more realistic predictions. Verification of the 3D models was achieved by correlating diffusion predictions with analytical models, while assuming periodicity of flakes in the z -direction (by contrast, 2D models assume infinite lengths of flakes). In addition, 3D predictions were also compared with the previously presented 2D predictions to highlight advantages and limitations of the latter. Furthermore, it is expected that when in service the nanocomposite would experience stress. Hence, the effect of strain in the nanocomposite on diffusion, and permeation was also considered and compared with the permeation rate in an unstrained state.

Figure 1. Illustration of the barrier model.

Figure 2. Unit cell model with notation of variables.

Figure 3. (a) Flake angle. (b) Maximum flake angle, achieved when top and bottom adjacent flakes first come into contact.

2 3D FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

ABAQUS FE software solver is used to predict diffusion, and permeation, through the nanocomposite. A 3D model with uniformly distributed flakes that would correlate with an analytical solution is first developed. Based on successful verification, the model is then further developed for angled flakes and for stress-assisted diffusion, both of which currently do not have known accurate analytical solutions.

2.1 Model Verification

The model for correlation is based on the 3D unit cell shown in Figure 4. The flake arrangement is also shown as viewed in plan and side cross-sectional views, which can be represented by Figure 2, where the variables include flake length, $2d$, and half thickness, $a/2$, distance between flakes, b , and slit width, $2c$. Square flakes, per the x-z plane, are assumed in this study.

The unit cell is assigned equal left and right boundaries and equal front and back boundaries to represent a periodic boundary condition. Based on Figure 4, the four corners of the unit cell are also represented by the equation for concentration, U :

$$U_A + U_D - U_B - U_C = 0 \quad \dots (1)$$

Figure 4. 3D diffusion unit cell with illustration of flake arrangement.

The 3D analytical solution for random nanocomposite systems by Minelli [5] is used for correlation, as described by the following equations. It is important to note that Minelli's model has been verified with experimental and numerical data with good correlation.

For $r < 1$

$$\frac{D_0}{D_{ff}} = \frac{\phi}{2\alpha} (\alpha + 2)^2 + \frac{2\phi}{\pi\alpha} (\alpha + 2)^2 \ln \left[\frac{2}{\pi} \frac{\alpha}{\phi(\alpha+2)} - 1 \right]^{-1} + \frac{\phi^2(\alpha+2)^4}{4(\alpha^2 - \alpha\phi(\alpha+2))} \dots (2)$$

For $r \geq 1$

$$\frac{D_0}{D_{ff}} = \frac{\phi}{2} (\alpha + 2) + \frac{2\phi}{\pi\alpha} (\alpha + 2)^2 \ln \left[\frac{(\alpha+2)}{\pi} \right] \dots (3)$$

where

D_0 is the diffusivity of a pure matrix;

D_{ff} is the diffusivity of a flake-filled nanocomposite;

α is the aspect ratio of the flake, given by the ratio of half length and thickness of flake, d/a ;

σ is the slit shape, given by the ratio of half slit width and thickness of flake, c/a ;

ϕ is the flake loading (by volume) in the matrix; and

r is a parameter that defines the range in which the respective Equations 2 and 3 hold true, given by Equation 4.

$$r = \frac{2(\alpha - \phi(\alpha+2))}{\phi(\alpha+2)^2} \dots (4)$$

The FE unit cell has a fixed width, and flake percentage by volume varies between 0.48% and 6.75%. The slit width, $2c$, between adjacent flakes is set at 0.1 unit, flake aspect ratio is set at 66, while the unit cell thickness (and, hence, perpendicular distance between flakes) is dependent on the flake percentage.

2.2 Angled Flakes

Flake orientation in real-life nanocomposite is not expected to be always perpendicular to the direction of permeant flow. Hence, it is useful to understand how angled flakes would affect diffusion and permeation. Based on the verified 3D FE model, unit cells with angled flakes are analysed to predict the behaviour as a function of flake angle. There are no known accurate analytical solutions.

In this study, the aspect ratio of the flakes are maintained at 198. When changing the flake angle θ , the planar flakes are only rotated about the z axis, as depicted in the side cross-sectional view of Figure 3a. A multi-plane angle is not considered here. For purpose of comparison, the angle is calculated, as per Equation 5, relative to the maximum flake angle, θ_{max} shown in Figure 3b, where $\theta_{rel}=0$ is when the flakes are perpendicular to the direction of permeant flow, and $\theta_{rel}=1$ is when flakes are at θ_{max} . The improvement in diffusion/permeation barrier of a given flake configuration, $(D_0/D_{ff})_{\theta}$ $\left(\frac{D_0}{D_{ff}}\right)_{\theta}$, is also calculated, using Equation 6, relative to barrier due to the zero angled flake, *i.e.* $\theta = 0$, configuration for slit width $2c$, $\left(\frac{D_0}{D_{ff}}\right)_{\theta=0}$.

$$\theta_{rel} = \frac{\theta}{\theta_{max}} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$D_{\theta} = \frac{\left(\frac{D_0}{D_{ff}}\right)_{\theta}}{\left(\frac{D_0}{D_{ff}}\right)_{\theta=0}} \quad \dots (6)$$

In addition to a range of flake angles, two slit widths - $2c$ and $6c$ - are also considered, with the purpose of investigating any combined effects of the two parameters on diffusion/permeation barrier. The volumetric loadings of flakes are, respectively, 0.98% and 0.92%, for the $2c$ and $6c$ slit width cases. The 3D predictions are also compared with those of the 2D models to show differences and similarities.

2.3 Stress-Assisted Analyses

The effects of stress on diffusion/permeation barrier is studied taking the permeation of CO₂ gas through LDPE (low-density polyethylene), as an example. Theoretically the model developed here is applicable to any combination of diffusivity and material. Table 1 summarises the main properties from the literature [6,7] used in the analyses. Tensile loads are applied to the unit cell and the stress analysis is coupled with the diffusion analysis to simulate the diffusion/permeation barrier behaviour with respect to stress experienced by the nanocomposite. A range of tensile loads is considered to explore the sensitivity to stress of the barrier performance.

Table 1. LDPE material properties & permeation of CO₂ gas.

Variables	Values
Diffusivity, D [6]	$6.7 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$
Solubility, S [6]	$3.3 \text{ cm}^3(\text{STP})/\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{MPa}$
Universal gas constant, R	8.31432 J/mol.K
Partial molar volume, \bar{V}_H [7]	$44.5 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Model Verification

Figure 5 shows a comparison between the 3D FEA predictions in this study and the Minelli analytical solution. The numerical D_o/D_{ff} correlates well with the Minelli solution for the range of flake volumetric loadings considered in this study. Based on the results, the FEA predictions are slightly more conservative compared to the analytical solution.

The 3D model requires large computational resources to set-up and to run the analysis. For example, the model with flake loading of 6.75% has more than 2 Million 8-noded brick elements to give satisfactory results. On 12 parallel processors, this analysis takes approximately 30 mins to complete. By contrast, a 2D model with higher mesh density is much simpler to set up, and requires only 90,000 elements and approximately 2 mins to complete the analysis on a single processor.

The 2D model assumes infinite length of flakes perpendicular to the plane, so D_o/D_{ff} is higher than that of the 3D model, which assumes finite-sized, square flakes. It is observed that the 3D predictions are approximately half of those from the 2D analysis, up to a flake loading of approximately 3.5%, as shown in Figure 6.

3.2 Effects of Flakes Angles

Figure 7a shows the concentration distributions obtained for a unit cell 3D model with flake angle, $\theta_{rel} = 0.9$. The cross-section of the model is shown in Figure 7b, where diffusion of the permeants around the top and bottom flakes are visible. It can be observed that the flakes effectively create a tortuous path, hence reducing the concentration of permeants at the top surface to where the permeants are flowing.

Like previously reported 2D predictions, the 3D models show the effect of angled flakes in increasing diffusion/permeation barrier with increasing flake angle from $\theta_{rel} = 0$, as shown in Figure 8. This seems to contradict the common understanding of tortuosity, where zero angled flakes create the most tortuous path for permeants. However, as mentioned above, due to the fixed unit cell thickness, the angled flakes are forced closer together as well, thus constricting the pathway of permeants. Apart from that, the arrangement of flakes remain regularly spaced, albeit at an angle.

Figure 5. 3D numerical predictions compared with analytical solution for uniform flakes.

Figure 6. 3D numerical predictions compared with 2D numerical predictions for uniform flakes.

Figure 7. Concentration distribution for flake angle, $\theta_{rel} = 0.9$:
For (a) whole model; (b) cross-sectional view mid-way in z -axis.

Figure 8. 3D model predictions of relative barrier, D_θ , for range of flake angles, θ_{rel} .

Another observation is that the two different slit widths show a similar trend, even though they have a three times size difference. The mean D_θ for slit width $2c$ and $6c$ are 1.67 and 1.61, respectively, for the entire range of flake angles considered in this work. By calculating a sample t-test of unequal variance, it is shown that there is no significant statistical difference (at 95% confidence level) between

the two cases, as can also be seen in Figure 9 where both standard deviation bars are overlapping. This observation is also noted for the 2D models. In Figure 10, the same comparison between mean D_θ for the two widths is shown using 2D data. Though 2D models predict larger barrier improvements, the same qualitative observation can be made, *i.e.* slit width is not a main factor controlling the barrier effect of flakes in a nanocomposite. The advantage of using 2D models to study trends like this allows quick screening to eliminate non-critical factors.

Figure 9. Comparison of mean D_θ , with standard deviation bars, from 3D model predictions of relative barrier performance for two different slit widths: 2c and 6c

Figure 10. Comparison of mean D_θ , with standard deviation bars, from 2D model predictions of relative barrier performance for two different slit widths: 2c and 6c (based on [4]).

3.3 Effects of Stress

Figure 11 shows the concentration distribution in an unstressed unit cell, where D_o/D_{ff} is 2.72. When stressed, the concentration distribution evolves as shown in Figure 12 with loads 3.5 MPa and 35 MPa. D_o/D_{ff} drops with increasing load giving values of 2.69 and 2.49, respectively. The drop in barrier performance can be related to the increased concentration in regions with high local stresses, like the edges of the flakes. This is shown in Figure 13, where the hydrostatic stress is higher in the region of both ends of the outlet slit. A plot of concentration across one of the outlet slits in Figure 14 shows that with increasing applied stress, the concentration is higher hence resulting in higher diffusion/permeation rates.

Figure 11: Concentration distribution (without stress).

(a)

(b)

Figure 12: Concentration distribution (with stress):
(a) 3.5 MPa load, and (b) 35 MPa load.

Fig. 13: Hydrostatic stress distribution in the unit cell for 35MPa load.

Figure 14: Concentration distribution across the outlet slit

4 CONCLUSION

A 3D FE model has been developed to predict diffusion and permeation through a nanocomposite. The influence of flake angles and slit width has been investigated, showing the width to be a non-critical variable in the diffusion/permeation barrier compared to flake angle and volumetric percentage. This is important because in real-life applications, flakes are not equally spaced, and this finding has shown that a nominal slit width value could be used to still provide good predictions.

The analyses show that increasing flake angles cause increase in D_{θ} such that a mean value of D_{θ} can be calculated for a range of angles to represent the average barrier improvement of a unit cell, for a specific flake aspect ratio and volumetric loading, ϕ . Further investigation into this could cover different orientations for different flakes in the same unit cell.

Stress in the nanocomposite has been shown to decrease the barrier property, though not significantly. High hydrostatic stresses around the edges of flakes serve to increase the concentration of permeants and increase the rate of diffusion.

Finally, comparisons between 3D and 2D FE models demonstrate the advantages of 2D models to conduct quick screening of non-critical variables in order to simplify 3D models and their analysis.

Thus, computational time can be greatly reduced while still being able to capture important trends. This was demonstrated here for the combined effects of slit width and flake angles.

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